

Paper 10

**STUDENT PERCEPTION TOWARDS MODERN
EDUCATION SYSTEM-A STUDY WITH REFERNCE
TO SELECTED COLLEGES OF MANGALURU CITY.**

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ABSTRACT

Education is the imparting and acquiring of knowledge through teaching and learning especially at a schools or similar institution. It plays very important role in human life. The earliest educational process involved sharing information ,about gathering food and providing shelter, learning language and acquiring the religious values, behaviour or practices of given culture. Before the invention reading and writing. In earlier days the schools, colleges, and other institutions were used the traditional way of educational system, but in present days it may come down and the modern education system is using to learning education. Modern education system includes a variety of technology, computer, projectors, internet and many more. Instead of using black board they are used smart boards, power point presentation. This will help the students to learn the skills, knowledge and easily accessing information. So keeping in this mind the study has been conducted and main goal is to know the perception towards modern education system and to study the impact of modern education system towards students of Mangaluru city.For the purpose of the study both primary data and secondary data has been collected. Primary data is from the students of Mangaluru city through distributing questionnaires where as secondary data is from the internet, newspaper.

Key words: modern education system, students, technologies.

INTRODUCTION:

The term “Education” is derived from the Latin word, ‘educatio’ which means a breeding, a bringing up. The education is the act or process of acquiring or imparting general knowledge, developing the powers of reasoning, judgement and generally of preparing oneself or others intellectually for mature life. Educational method includes storytelling, discussion, teaching, training and directed research. Education is commonly divided formally into such stages as preschool or kindergarten, primary school, secondary school and then college, university. In earlier days these educational institutions were used the traditional way of education system

(black boards). But it may come down in present days and they are using modern education system say smart boards, projectors, power point presentation , internet basis desktop,,etc. These modern technologies will help the students can learn anywhere and both students and teachers benefited from new technologies. This modern education system helping to change education in a positive way: it is part of modern world, technological education is improving grades for the student and it prepares them for the future.

Objectives:

- 1) To know the perception of student towards modern education system.
- 2) To study the impact of modern education system towards students.

Methodology:

Based on requirement of the study data has been collected from the various secondary sources such as PDF files, internet, and published books. And at the same time the way of structured interview method. The relevant data has been collected to study the perception towards modern education system. The samples were the students of selected colleges of Mangaluru city only. Randomly selected 100 samples were interviewed with structured set of questionnaires.

Limitation:

- 1) The study reveals student perception towards modern education system of only selected colleges of Mangaluru city (such as University college hampanakatta, University college konaje and Canara College).
- 2) This paper reveals only positive impact of modern education system.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

The survey results are organised as follows. In the first section the demographic profile of respondents is presented, where this section has classified into categories and 100 respondents is taken into consideration.

Profile of respondents;

The selected 100 respondents include students of selected colleges of Mangaluru city. Profile of respondent on the basis of gender, age and education are presented below;

Table 1: Gender wise distribution of samples

Gender	No of respondents	percentages
Male	34	34
Female	66	66
Transgender	-	-
Total	100	100

Table 2: Age wise distribution of samples

Age	No of respondents	percentages
18 to 20	18	18

21 to 23	78	78
24 to 26	4	4
Total	100	100

Table 3: Education qualification wise distribution of samples

Education	No of respondents	percentages
UG	46	46
PG	54	54
Total	100	100

The above table reveals the demographic profile of the respondent. On the basis of demographic profile, the following analysis and interpretations are made.

Table 4: preferable “Education system”

Education system	No of respondents	percentages
Traditional education system	10	10
Modern education system	90	90
Total	100	100

Table 4 reveals that 90% of the students are preferable with the modern education system, because of its effectiveness.

Table 5: Smart board facility

Perception	No of respondents	percentages
Yes	20	20
No	80	80
Total	100	100

The study reveals that out of 100 respondents, 80% of them are not having smart board facility in their college. It may be due to lack of fund and illiteracy about the modern teaching method like using smart boards, power point presentation etc.

Table 6: Rating of Modern education system

Rating	No of respondents	percentages
Excellent	10	10
Good	66	66
Average	24	24
Bad	-	-

Total	100	100
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Table 6 reveals that ratings of modern education system. Out of 100 respondents, 10% of them rated as Excellent, 66% of them rated as Good, and 24% respondents are rated as Average.

Table 7: Benefits from modern education system

Benefits	No of respondents	percentages
Path to digitalization	52	52
Qualitative information	28	28
Eco –friendly	20	20
Total	100	100

Table 7 states that 52% of the respondents say, modern education system is a path to digitalization. 28% of them said modern education system provides qualitative information and 20% of the respondents were said this system is Eco- friendly. To reinforce the positive benefits that students are receiving since the integration of the technology into our education curriculum. Over the last few years, the learning and teaching environment has changed and we as a community need to adherence to all the research that states technology has been used to effectively enhance the teaching and learning experience and is essential and necessary in today’s competitive economy.

Table 8: facilities for modern education system

Facilities	No of respondents	percentages
Internet on desktop	16	16
Smart board	32	32
Projector/PPT	52	52
Total	100	100

Majority of the respondent’s states that 52% of them getting projectors facility from their institution. 32% as a smart board facility and 16% as an internet on desktop. Modern education system is aided with varieties of technology, like internet, projectors, PPT, smart board, video based and so on. Technology is something to strongly believe in and should be used as learning tools in helping not only students, but teachers’ achieve higher level in and out of the classroom. Belief that there is a positive impact of technology on teaching and student performance has been questioned by so many, but with the ample amount of research available that proves technology has a valuable place in our educational system.

Table 9: Effective modes of teaching through PPT

Modes	No of respondents	percentages
Pictures	28	28
Videos	50	50
Animation colours	22	22
Total	100	100

The table states that out of 100 respondents, 50% of the students were said that use videos in PPT is the effective modes of teaching and 28% use as pictures and 22% as animation colours can make more effective modes of teaching. Numerous people in today's society want the use of technology readily available in the schools, but are unsure of the proper use of technology. With the continuous learning and teaching students and teachers will benefit if technology is used accordingly. There has clearly been a turning point as we continue to see the evidence of a new excitement for learning in our educational system

Table 10: Impact of Modern education system on students

Impact	No of respondents	percentages
Skill development	56	56
New teaching methods	20	20
Improves student attitude	10	10
Growth of technology	14	14
Total	100	100

Table 10 states that 56% of the respondents opines that modern education system has its impact on the skill development and 20% of them said this system introduces new teaching methods and 10% of them said it will improve student attitude towards education and 14% of the students felt that it helps in developing the new teaching system through the technology. There is a new determination for teachers that are constantly being driven by the students, whom are excited by the integration of technology usage in the classroom. When technology is applied in a student's everyday life, a positive outcome will always arise from it.

Major finding of the study:

Most of the respondents were female that is 66% and they belongs to the age group (21 to 23) that consist of 78% of the total respondents in which most of them are PG students i.e. 54%. Majority of the respondents that is 90% are preferable with the modern education system. But 80% of the students are not having smart board facility from their institution

It is found in the study that majority of the respondents (that is 66%) are agree with modern education system and they felt it is good and most of them that is 52% were said modern education system is right way to get digitalization.

As per this study 52% of the respondents are having projector or power point presentation facility in their institution and 50% of them are think that using videos, as a provision to make more effective modes of teaching through PPT is a good move to gain the attention of students towards subject.

The study reveals that 56% of the respondents felt that Skill development is main impact of modern education system

It is found that modern education system is positively affected on the education system and some of the institutions are not having proper technologies regarding modern education system and students are more interesting in learn the modern education system, but they are not getting well trained people and smart people to teach them.

Suggestions:

As the country is moving towards digitalization, it is necessary for every student to have some knowledge about modern technologies, in order to survive with the competitive world. If any institution makes an provision to every student have to access such technologies it will help the student to be confident

The government has to mainly focusing on skill based education and this system should be implementing in all schools and colleges compulsory. This may contribute in improving the quality of the education.

The government should train the teachers about effective utilisation of the modern teaching method by providing proper training.

Conclusion:

Technology is all around us no matter where we go, where we live in such high-tech society and job market that our students need adequate training to ensure they will be given the proper tools deemed necessary to be successful. With the technology market so prevent in our everyday lives, we as students, teachers, parents and administrators need to come together and compile a plan on how to incorporate the use of technology into our teaching and learning.

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